

[Benzthiazoloneyl Quinazolines.

By PRAFULLA KUMAR BOSE AND KUMUD BEHARI PATHAK.

Complex heterocyclic systems containing the quinazoline ring have been synthesised by Asahina, Manske and Robinson (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 1708) and by Aggarwal and Rây (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 723) by the method of Sen and Rây (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 646), which consisted in condensing suitable cyclic amides with anthranilic acid in presence of phosphorus trichloride. This method, however, failed in the case of α -hydroxyquinolines, but by replacing the hydroxyl group by of chlorine, the desired results were obtained (Bose and Sen, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 2840). This modified method has now been applied to fuse a quinazoline ring to benzthiazoles, thus :

The benzthiazoloneyl quinazolines (III), thus obtained, are stable compounds and can be easily nitrated. The intermediate acids could not be isolated from the reaction products, but they are indirectly obtained by hydrolysis of (III). The substances are expected to be physiologically active,

EXPERIMENTAL.

The chlorobenzthiazoles used in this investigation were prepared by the method of Hofmann, the yields being generally poor (*Ber.*, 1879, 12, 1126).

*1-Chlorobenzthiazole and anthranilic acid: Formation of (III).—*Molecular quantities of the components were carefully heated over a small flame, which was withdrawn as soon as the reaction became vigorous. The horny mass obtained on cooling was extracted with ammonia to remove any unchanged anthranilic acid. The insoluble residue was crystallised from a mixture of pyridine and alcohol. It formed slender needles, m.p. 189°. (Found: C, 66.48; H, 3.12; N, 10.9; S, 12.5. $C_{14}H_8ON_2S$ requires C, 66.6; H, 3.17; N, 14.1; S, 12.7 per cent).

*Hydrolysis of above: Formation of (I) or (II).—*The substance (0.4 g.) was refluxed with 25 c.c. of 5% alcoholic potassium hydroxide for 3 hours. The solution was acidified with acetic acid and the precipitate crystallised from acetone as colourless needles, m.p. 187°. The substance is acidic to litmus and decomposed sodium bicarbonate in the cold. (Found: N, 10.39. $C_{14}H_{10}O_2N_2S$ requires N, 10.37 per cent). Acetic anhydride converted it into the parent substance (III) by extracting a molecule of water. The *sodium salt* was prepared by treating an alcoholic solution of the acid with alcoholic sodium hydroxide. On recrystallisation from alcohol it melted at 273°. (Found: Na, 7.8. $C_{14}H_9O_2N_2SNa$ requires Na, 7.9 per cent).

*Nitration of (III).—*To a cooled mixture of 1 c.c. fuming nitric acid and 1 c.c. concentrated sulphuric acid was gradually added 0.5 g. of the substance. After a few minutes the yellow solution was poured into crushed ice and the precipitate collected. It formed yellow needles from hot acetic acid, m.p. 279-80°. (Found: N, 16.65. $C_{14}H_6ON_2S(NO_2)_2$ requires N, 16.4 per cent).

1-Chloro-5-methylbenzthiazole was prepared by Hofmann's method and was obtained as colourless needles from cold methyl alcohol, m.p. 42°. Hunter (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 2206) described this substance as an oil, b.p. 148.52°/15 mm. On condensation with anthranilic acid, the corresponding benzthiazoloneyl quinazoline was obtained as colourless needles, m.p. 226°. (Found: C, 67.63; H, 3.77; N, 10.43. $C_{15}H_{10}ON_2S$ requires C, 67.66; H, 3.75; N, 10.5 per cent). Hydrolysis with alcoholic alkali led to the formation of a crystalline

acid, m.p. 188-89°. (Found: N, 9.56. $C_{15}H_{12}O_2N_2S$ requires N, 9.8 per cent). It could be converted into the original compound by the action of hot acetic anhydride. The *sodium salt* melted at 280°. (Found: Na, 7.71. $C_{15}H_{11}O_2N_2SNa$ requires Na, 7.51 per cent). Nitration with a mixture of fuming nitric acid and sulphuric acid in the cold gave rise to two compounds: (i) A *dinitro*-compound, m.p. 280°, which separated from acetic acid as yellow star-like crystals, and (ii) a *mononitro*- compound which was less soluble in acetic acid and formed yellow needles from acetone, m.p. 304°. [Found: (i) N, 15.9. (ii) N, 13.7. $C_{15}H_8ON_2S(NO_2)_2$ requires N, 15.7 per cent. $C_{15}H_9ON_2S(NO_2)$ requires N, 13.5 per cent].

1-Chloro-3-methylbenzthiazole.—Attempts to prepare this by Hofmann's method (temperature range 130°-170°) or by Hunter's modification of the same method (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 1488) were not successful. By Sandmeyer's reaction the chlorobenzthiazole was obtained from the corresponding aminothiazole, but the yield was too poor to enable us to study its condensation with anthranilic acid.

1-Chloro-4-methylbenzthiazole and anthranilic acid gave the usual product crystallising as colourless needles from a mixture of pyridine and alcohol, m.p. 180°. (Found: N, 10.53. $C_{15}H_{10}ON_2S$ requires N, 10.52 per cent). The corresponding *acid* melted at 189°. (Found: N, 9.5. $C_{15}H_{12}O_2N_2S$ requires N, 9.8 per cent).

α-Naphthothiazolonefyl Quinazoline.

It was obtained in the form of colourless prisms (m.p. 261°) by condensing 1-chloro-*α*-naphthothiazole (m.p. 75°) with anthranilic acid in the usual way. (Found: N, 9.25. $C_{18}H_{10}ON_2S$ requires N, 9.27 per cent).

